

INVERSION OF TWO CYCLOTOMIC MATRICES

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Abstract

Let $n \geq 3$ be a square-free natural number. We explicitly describe the inverses of the matrices

$$(2 \sin(2\pi j k^* / n))_{j,k} \quad \text{and} \quad (2 \cos(2\pi j k^* / n))_{j,k},$$

where k^* denotes a multiplicative inverse of $k \bmod n$ and j, k run through the set $\{l; 1 \leq l \leq n/2, (l, n) = 1\}$. These results are based on cyclotomy, in particular, on the theory of Gauss sums.

1. Introduction and Results

In the paper [3] Lehmer states that there are only few classes of matrices for which explicit formulas for the determinants, the eigenvalues and the inverses are known. He gives a number of examples of this kind. Further examples can be found in the papers [1], [4], [6] and [5]. All of these examples are based on number theory. The closest analogue of the matrices considered here is contained in the article [5], namely, the matrix

$$(\sin(\pi j k / n))_{j,k},$$

where $1 \leq j, k \leq n, (jk, n) = 1$. The author of [5] determines the characteristic polynomial of this matrix, the respective eigenvalues being divisors of n or equal to 0. But the multiplicities of these eigenvalues are quite involved. In the present paper the eigenvalues of similar matrices S and C turn out to be Gauss sums belonging to Dirichlet characters mod n . The main results, however, are explicit formulas for the inverses S^{-1} and C^{-1} in the cases when these matrices are invertible. This is in contrast to the papers we have quoted, since explicit formulas for inverses are scarcely given there.

Let $n \geq 3$ be a natural number. Let \mathcal{R} denote a system of representatives of the group $(\mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}n)^\times / \{\pm 1\}$. Suppose that \mathcal{R} is ordered in some way. Typically, \mathcal{R} is the set $\{k; 1 \leq k \leq n/2, (k, n) = 1\}$ with its natural order. For $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, $(k, n) = 1$, let k^*

denote a multiplicative inverse of $k \pmod n$ (so $kk^* \equiv 1 \pmod n$). We define

$$s_k = 2 \sin(2\pi k/n) \quad \text{and} \quad c_k = 2 \cos(2\pi k/n),$$

where $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, $(k, n) = 1$. We consider the matrices

$$S = (s_{jk^*})_{j,k \in \mathcal{R}} \quad \text{and} \quad C = (c_{jk^*})_{j,k \in \mathcal{R}},$$

which we call the *sine matrix* and the *cosine matrix*, respectively.

We think that the matrices S and C deserve some interest not only because of their simple structure but also by reason of their connection with cyclotomy, in particular, with Gauss sums (see [7] for the history of this topic).

In order to be able to enunciate our main results, we define

$$\lambda(k) = |\{q; q \geq 3, q \mid n, k \equiv 1 \pmod q\}| \tag{1}$$

for $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, $(k, n) = 1$. Furthermore, put

$$\widehat{s}_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{R}} (\lambda(lk) - \lambda(-lk))s_l, \tag{2}$$

for $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, $(k, n) = 1$. For the same numbers k put

$$\widehat{c}_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{R}} (\lambda(lk) + \lambda(-lk) + \rho_n)c_l, \tag{3}$$

with

$$\rho_n = \begin{cases} 2, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd;} \\ 4, & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

Our main results are as follows.

Theorem 1. *The sine matrix S is invertible if, and only if, n is square-free or $n = 4$. In this case*

$$S^{-1} = (\widehat{s}_{jk^*})_{j,k \in \mathcal{R}},$$

with \widehat{s}_{jk^*} defined by (2).

Theorem 2. *The cosine matrix C is invertible if, and only if, n is square-free. In this case*

$$C^{-1} = (\widehat{c}_{jk^*})_{j,k \in \mathcal{R}}$$

with \widehat{c}_{jk^*} defined by (3).

Remark. If the sine matrix S is invertible, then the numbers s_l , $l \in \mathcal{R}$, are \mathbb{Q} -linearly independent. This can be seen by application of Galois automorphisms of the n th cyclotomic field $\mathbb{Q}(\zeta_n)$ to a relation $\sum_{l \in \mathcal{R}} \lambda_l i s_l = 0$ with $\lambda_l \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $i s_l = \zeta_n^l - \zeta_n^{-l}$.

Accordingly, the representation (2) of \widehat{s}_k as a rational linear combination of the numbers $s_l, l \in \mathcal{R}$, is unique in this case. The same holds in the case of the cosine matrix and (3).

The entries of S have the form $\pm s_l, l \in \mathcal{R}$. This is due to the fact that

$$s_{jk^*} = \varepsilon s_l$$

with $\varepsilon \in \{\pm 1\}, l \in \mathcal{R}$, if $jk^* \equiv \varepsilon l \pmod n$. In the same way we have

$$\widehat{s}_{jk^*} = \varepsilon \widehat{s}_l$$

if $jk^* \equiv \varepsilon l \pmod n$. This means that it suffices to compute the numbers \widehat{s}_l only for $l \in \mathcal{R}$ in order to write down the matrix S^{-1} . Indeed, this matrix arises from S if we replace each entry εs_l of S by the respective entry $\varepsilon \widehat{s}_l$.

The same procedure works in the case of the cosine matrix, whose entries have the form $c_l, l \in \mathcal{R}$.

Examples. 1. Let $n = 15$ and $\mathcal{R} = \{1, 2, 4, 7\}$. Then S can be written

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} s_1 & -s_7 & s_4 & -s_2 \\ s_2 & s_1 & -s_7 & -s_4 \\ s_4 & s_2 & s_1 & s_7 \\ s_7 & -s_4 & -s_2 & s_1 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{5}$$

Theorem 1 yields $\widehat{s}_1 = (3s_1 - s_2 + s_7)/15, \widehat{s}_2 = (-s_1 - s_4 - 3s_7)/15, \widehat{s}_4 = (-s_2 + 3s_4 + s_7)/15,$ and $\widehat{s}_7 = (s_1 - 3s_2 + s_4)/15$. We obtain S^{-1} if we put a circumflex on each s occurring in (5).

2. Let $n = 35$ and $\mathcal{R} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 16, 17\}$. In the case of the cosine matrix we have

$$\widehat{c}_1 = \frac{1}{35}(5c_1 + 2c_2 + 2c_3 + 3c_4 + 4c_6 + 3c_8 + 3c_9 + 3c_{11} + 2c_{12} + 3c_{13} + 3c_{16} + 2c_{17}).$$

The remaining elements \widehat{c}_l have the same coefficients in a permuted order.

Remark. If $n = p$ is a prime, Theorem 1 shows that S^{-1} is particularly simple, namely, $S^{-1} = \frac{1}{p}S^t$ (S^t is the transpose of S). There is no analogue for the cosine matrix. For instance, if $p = 7$ and $\mathcal{R} = \{1, 2, 3\}$, we have $\widehat{c}_1 = (3c_1 + 2c_2 + 2c_3)/7$. The prime number case of the sine matrix can also be settled by means of a simple trigonometric argument. This, however, seems to be hardly possible if n consists of at least two prime factors $p > q \geq 3$.

2. Proofs

First we prove Theorem 1, then we indicate the changes required by the proof of Theorem 2. Let \mathcal{X} denote the set of Dirichlet characters mod n , and \mathcal{X}^- and \mathcal{X}^+

the subsets of odd and even characters, respectively. The matrix S is connected with \mathcal{X}^- , whereas C is connected with \mathcal{X}^+ . We note the orthogonality relation

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \chi(k) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } k \not\equiv \pm 1 \pmod n; \\ \varphi(n)/2, & \text{if } k \equiv 1 \pmod n; \\ -\varphi(n)/2, & \text{if } k \equiv -1 \pmod n, \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

see [2, p. 210]. Here $(k, n) = 1$ and φ denotes Euler's function.

Suppose that the set \mathcal{X}^- is ordered in some way. Then we can define the matrix

$$X = \sqrt{n/\varphi(n)}(\chi(k))_{k \in \mathcal{R}, \chi \in \mathcal{X}^-}.$$

Since $|\mathcal{R}| = |\mathcal{X}^-| = \varphi(n)/2$, X is a square matrix. We note the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *The matrix X is unitary, i.e., $X^{-1} = \overline{X}^t$ (the transpose of the complex-conjugate matrix).*

Proof. This is an immediate consequence of the orthogonality relation (6) (observe that $\overline{\chi}(k) = \chi(k^*)$). □

Let $\zeta_n = e^{2\pi i/n}$ be the standard primitive n th root of unity. For $\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-$ let

$$\tau(\chi) = \sum_{k=1}^n \chi(k)\zeta_n^k \tag{7}$$

be the corresponding Gauss sum, see [2, p. 445]. We consider the diagonal matrix

$$T = \text{diag}(\tau(\overline{\chi}))_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-}.$$

Proposition 1. *The sine matrix S is normal. Indeed,*

$$\overline{X}^t SX = -iT.$$

Proof. We show $XT\overline{X}^t = iS$. Obviously, the entry $(XT\overline{X}^t)_{j,k}$ equals

$$\frac{2}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \chi(j)\tau(\overline{\chi})\overline{\chi}(k) = \frac{2}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \chi(jk^*) \sum_{(l,n)=1} \chi(l^*)\zeta_n^l,$$

where the index l satisfies $1 \leq l \leq n$, $(l, n) = 1$. This can be written

$$\frac{2}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{(l,n)=1} \zeta_n^l \sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \chi(jk^*l^*).$$

Now the orthogonality relation (6), together with $\zeta_n^l - \zeta_n^{-l} = is_l$, shows that this is just is_{jk^*} . □

In order to study the vanishing of the eigenvalues of S , we use the reduction formula

$$\tau(\bar{\chi}) = \mu\left(\frac{n}{f_\chi}\right) \bar{\chi}_f\left(\frac{n}{f_\chi}\right) \tau(\bar{\chi}_f), \tag{8}$$

see [2, p. 448]. Here μ means the Möbius function, f_χ the conductor of the character χ , χ_f the primitive character belonging to χ (which is a Dirichlet character mod f_χ) and $\tau(\bar{\chi}_f)$ the Gauss sum

$$\sum_{k=1}^{f_\chi} \bar{\chi}_f(k) \zeta_{f_\chi}^k.$$

Since

$$\tau(\chi_f)\tau(\bar{\chi}_f) = -f_\chi \tag{9}$$

(see [2, p. 269]), formula (8) shows when the eigenvalue $-i\tau(\bar{\chi})$ vanishes. We obtain the following result.

Proposition 2. *The matrix S is invertible if, and only if, n is square-free or $n = 4$.*

Proof. If n is square-free, then n/f_χ is square-free and $(f_\chi, n/f_\chi) = 1$. By (8) and (9), all Gauss sums $\tau(\chi)$ are different from 0. If $n = 4$ and $\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-$, then $f_\chi = 4$ and $n/f_\chi = 1$.

Conversely, suppose that n is not square-free and different from 4. Then one of the following three cases occurs. There is a prime $p \geq 3$ such that $p^2 | n$, or $4p | n$, or $8 | n$. In the first and the second case there is a character $\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-$ with $f_\chi = p$. Accordingly, $\chi_f(n/f_\chi) = 0$ or $\mu(n/f_\chi) = 0$. In the third case there is a character $\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-$ with $f_\chi = 4$. Therefore, $\chi_f(n/f_\chi) = 0$. \square

Lemma 2. *Let n be square-free or equal to 4. For $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, $(k, n) = 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \frac{\chi(k)}{f_\chi} = \frac{\varphi(n)}{2n} (\lambda(k) - \lambda(-k)),$$

the λ 's being defined by (1).

Proof. Obviously,

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \frac{\chi(k)}{f_\chi} = \sum_{d|n} \frac{1}{d} \sum_{\substack{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^- \\ f_\chi=d}} \chi(k).$$

Möbius inversion gives

$$\sum_{\substack{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^- \\ f_\chi=d}} \chi(k) = \sum_{q|d} \mu\left(\frac{d}{q}\right) \sum_{f_\chi|q} \chi(k).$$

Here we note that the characters $\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-$ with $f_\chi | q$ are in one-to-one correspondence with the odd Dirichlet characters mod q . Indeed, if $\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-$, one defines the Dirichlet character $\chi_q \pmod q$ in the following way. If $(j, q) = 1$, there is an integer l with $(l, n) = 1$ such that $l \equiv j \pmod q$. Then $\chi_q(j) = \chi(l)$; see [2, p. 217]. Accordingly,

$$\sum_{f_\chi | q} \chi(k) = \sum_{\chi_q} \chi_q(k).$$

From (6) we obtain

$$\sum_{\chi_q} \chi_q(k) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } q \leq 2 \text{ or } q \geq 3 \text{ and } k \not\equiv \pm 1 \pmod q; \\ \varphi(q)/2, & \text{if } q \geq 3 \text{ and } k \equiv 1 \pmod q; \\ -\varphi(q)/2, & \text{if } q \geq 3 \text{ and } k \equiv -1 \pmod q \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

(observe that there are no odd characters χ_q if $q \leq 2$). Therefore, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^- \\ f_\chi = d}} \chi(k) = \sum_{\substack{q | d, q \geq 3 \\ k \equiv \pm 1 \pmod q}} \pm \mu\left(\frac{d}{q}\right) \frac{\varphi(q)}{2},$$

where the \pm sign in the summand corresponds to the respective sign in the summation index. If we write $d = q \cdot r$, we have

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \frac{\chi(k)}{f_\chi} = \sum_{\substack{q | n, q \geq 3 \\ k \equiv \pm 1 \pmod q}} \pm \frac{\varphi(q)}{2} \sum_{r | \frac{n}{q}} \frac{\mu(r)}{qr}.$$

Since

$$\sum_{r | \frac{n}{q}} \frac{\mu(r)}{r} = \prod_{p | \frac{n}{q}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) = \frac{\varphi(n/q)}{n/q}$$

we obtain

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \frac{\chi(k)}{f_\chi} = \sum_{\substack{q | n, q \geq 3 \\ k \equiv \pm 1 \pmod q}} \pm \frac{\varphi(q)}{2q} \cdot \frac{\varphi(n/q)}{n/q}. \quad (11)$$

However, n is square-free or equal to 4, and so $\varphi(q)\varphi(n/q) = \varphi(n)$. This implies

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \frac{\chi(k)}{f_\chi} = \frac{\varphi(n)}{2n} (\lambda(k) - \lambda(-k)).$$

□

Proof of Theorem 1. By Proposition 1, $S^{-1} = iXT^{-1}\overline{X}^t$, which means that the entry $(S^{-1})_{j,k}$, $j, k \in \mathcal{R}$, of S^{-1} is given by

$$(S^{-1})_{j,k} = \frac{2i}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \chi(j)\tau(\overline{\chi})^{-1}\overline{\chi}(k).$$

From (8) and (9) we obtain

$$\tau(\overline{\chi})^{-1} = \frac{\mu(n/f_\chi)\chi_f(n/f_\chi)\tau(\chi_f)}{-f_\chi} = -\frac{\tau(\chi)}{f_\chi}.$$

Therefore,

$$(S^{-1})_{j,k} = \frac{-2i}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \frac{\chi(jk^*)}{f_\chi} \tau(\chi).$$

Now (7) yields

$$(S^{-1})_{j,k} = \frac{-2i}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{(l,n)=1} \zeta_n^l \sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^-} \frac{\chi(ljk^*)}{f_\chi}.$$

By Lemma 2,

$$(S^{-1})_{j,k} = \frac{-2i}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{(l,n)=1} \zeta_n^l \frac{\varphi(n)}{2n} (\lambda(ljk^*) - \lambda(-ljk^*)).$$

Altogether, we have

$$(S^{-1})_{j,k} = \frac{-i}{n} \sum_{(l,n)=1} \zeta_n^l (\lambda(ljk^*) - \lambda(-ljk^*)).$$

On observing that $s_l = -i(\zeta_n^l - \zeta_n^{-l})$, we obtain Theorem 1. □

The setting of the *proof of Theorem 2* is slightly different. Indeed, the unitary matrix X is defined by

$$X = \sqrt{n/\varphi(n)} (\chi(k))_{k \in \mathcal{R}, \chi \in \mathcal{X}^+}.$$

The cosine matrix C is normal, and $\overline{X}^t C X = T$, with $T = \text{diag}(\tau(\overline{\chi}))_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^+}$. In this case it is easy to see that T (and, hence, C) is invertible if, and only if, n is square-free. Instead of (9) we have

$$\tau(\chi_f)\tau(\overline{\chi}_f) = f_\chi.$$

The analogue of Lemma 2 reads

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^+} \frac{\chi(k)}{f_\chi} = \frac{\varphi(n)}{2n} (\lambda(k) + \lambda(-k) + \rho_n) \tag{12}$$

with ρ_n as in (4). This is due to the fact that the counterpart of formula (10) takes the form

$$\sum_{\chi_q} \chi_q(k) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } q \leq 2; \\ 0, & \text{if } q \geq 3 \text{ and } k \not\equiv \pm 1 \pmod q; \\ \varphi(q)/2, & \text{if } q \geq 3 \text{ and } k \equiv \pm 1 \pmod q. \end{cases}$$

Accordingly, formula (11) has the equivalent

$$\sum_{\chi \in \mathcal{X}^+} \frac{\chi(k)}{f_\chi} = \sum_{\substack{q|n, q \geq 3 \\ k \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{q}}} \frac{\varphi(q)}{2q} \cdot \frac{\varphi(n/q)}{n/q} + \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ 2 \nmid d}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d},$$

which gives (12). Up to these differences, the proof follows the pattern of the proof of Theorem 1.

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